

nonfloating rices (see table). Among floating rice varieties, plants with good elongation ability were more sensitive than those with moderate ability. The r^2 values for the correlation between elongation following flooding relative to internode length with GA₃ treatment was 0.40.

The GA₃ treatment did not reflect elongation ability during submergence in some cases. Submergence-tolerant variety

BKNFR76106-16-0-1, for example, had an exceptionally high internode length of 66 cm after GA₃ treatment, but it elongated the least among entries in the flooding treatment.

Plant elongation from short-duration flooding at early seedling stage was usually comparable to that with GA₃ treatment except in cases where elongating and nonelongating MVs did not differ much from the other.

Findings suggest that plant sensitivity to GA₃ may differ between floating and nonfloating rice varieties during at least the 5-6 wk stage.

Foliar application of 500 ppm GA₃ could be used during the seedling stage to distinguish floating rices possessing good elongation ability from those having poor elongation ability and from nonfloating rices. □

Integrated germplasm improvement—irrigated

Basmati 385 approved for cultivation in Punjab, India

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Basmati 385 was introduced from Pakistan. We evaluated it in the Punjab for yield, morphological traits, grain quality, and disease and insect resistance. Basmati 385 produced about 30% more rice than Basmati 370, but it was outyielded by Pusa Basmati 1 by about 4% in research and adaptive trials.

Yield data for the varieties under different N levels and dates of transplanting (Table 1) showed that 60 kg N/ha is optimum for Basmati 385 and Basmati 370, while 90 kg N/ha is optimum for Pusa Basmati 1 under normal soil fertility. The optimum time for transplanting is the first fortnight of July

Table 1. Yield of Basmati 385, Basmati 370, and Pusa Basmati 1 under different N levels and transplanting dates, 1991 wet season.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)		
	Basmati 385	Basmati 370	Pusa Basmati 1
N level (kg N/ha)			
0	3.2	2.1	3.5
60	4.3	3.3	4.6
90	4.3	3.2	4.9
120	4.3	3.1	5.0
Mean	4.0	3.1	4.5
Transplanting date			
15 Jun	3.9	3.1	4.4
30 Jun	4.3	3.3	4.8
15 Jul	4.1	4.2	3.8
25 Jul	3.4	2.3	3.6
Mean	4.1	3.2	4.1

for Basmati 385 and Basmati 370 and the second fortnight of June for Pusa Basmati 1.

Morphological and grain quality traits for the varieties are in Table 2. Grain shape and cooking quality of Basmati 385 are similar to those of Basmati 370. Although grains of Pusa Basmati 1 are longer and more slender than the rice of Basmati 370 and Basmati 385, cooking quality and head rice recovery of Pusa Basmati 1 is slightly inferior to that of the others. Pusa Basmati 1 received the lowest score of the three in a consumer acceptability test for cooking and eating quality of rice. Grain quality of Basmati 38.5 meets requirements for export to the Middle East, Europe, and the United States.

Basmati 385 matures earlier than Basmati 370 and Pusa Basmati 1. It has short plant height and sturdier stems than Basmati 370, but is taller than Pusa Basmati 1. The three varieties are equally susceptible to bacterial blight and stem borer, the two most serious pests of rice in the Punjab.

Krasnodarsky 86, a modern variety for use without pesticides in Kuban and Crimea, Russia

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Krasnodarsky 86 is a modern, multiple-resistant rice variety. The Russian Ministry of Agriculture released it in

Table 2. Morphological and grain quality characters of Basmati 385, Basmati 370, and Pusa Basmati 1.

Character	Basmati 385	Basmati 370	Pusa Basmati 1
Plant height (cm)	140	165	100
Days to maturity (no.)	135	150	140
Panicle-bearing tillers (no./m ²)	234	243	273
Spikelets (no./panicle)	210	140	168
Head rice recovery (%)	61.60	62.20	60.50
1000-grain wt (g)	15.80	15.70	16.50
Grain length (mm)	7.15	7.15	7.52
Grain breadth (mm)	1.65	1.63	1.56
Length-breadth ratio	4.33	4.39	4.82
Grain elongation ratio	1.94	1.95	1.80
Volume expansion	4.00	4.00	3.90
Amylose content (%)	23.52	23.48	22.85
Aroma	Strong	Strong	Mild

Because of its good grain quality and superiority in yield potential, earliness, and short plant height, the State Variety Approval Committee has approved Basmati 385 for general cultivation in the Punjab, India. □

1990 for the Kuban area (Krasnodarsky Territory and Republic of Adygea) and in 1992 for Crimea. It is already planted on 20,000 ha.

The variety was developed by individual selection and biotechnological methods from 40 lines segregated from Krasnodarsky 424 variety.

Krasnodarsky 86 belongs to the japonica subspecies. It is more resistant to lodging, blast, insects, and weeds than Krasnodarsky 424 and is recommended for cultivation without pesticides.